

Ultrafast Depolarization of Transient Absorption as a Probe of Plasmonicity of Optical Transitions in Ag Nanoclusters

Alessandra Paladini¹ · Daniele Catone² ·
Patrick O’Keeffe^{1,†} · Francesco Toschi¹ ·
Lorenza Suber³

Received: November 17, 2017/ Accepted: date

Abstract Time-resolved polarization dependent transient absorption has been used to study the plasmonicity of the optical transitions of Ag nanoparticles and nanoclusters. The lack of a measureable polarization anisotropy in the nanoparticles is indicative of the ultrafast electron-electron scattering while the anisotropy with a depolarization timescale of 500 fs observed in the nanoclusters indicates the excitation of a non-plasmonic state. The short lifetime of the anisotropy is a measure of electronic coupling between nearly degenerate states and is thus proposed as a sensitive measurement of the plasmonic content of the optical transitions of nanoclusters.

Keywords Nanocluster · Plasmon · Transient absorption · Time-resolved polarization anisotropy

1 Introduction

Ultrastable metal nanoclusters (NCs) are nanostructures with sizes ranging from the sub-nm to the few nm range. They are a class of nanostructures which merit a separate name (also sometimes called monolayer protected clusters, or intensely and broadly absorbing nanoparticles (IBANs) [1]) from nanoparticles, largely due to their structural and optoelectronic properties which are fundamentally different from nanoparticles of the same metal [2–4]. Thanks to these unique properties nanoclusters have found applications in biology [2,5], in solar cell technologies, [6] as catalysts [7] and in sensors [8]. A particularly interesting type of NC consists of a neutral metal core surrounded by a protective layer in which the metal atoms exhibit significant positive charges due to electron transfer to the ligands. This

¹Istituto di Struttura della Materia-CNR (ISM-CNR), Division of Ultrafast Processes in Materials (FLASHit), Area della Ricerca di Roma 1, Monterotondo Scalo, Italy.

² Istituto di Struttura della Materia-CNR (ISM-CNR), Division of Ultrafast Processes in Materials (FLASHit), Area della Ricerca di Roma Tor Vergata, 100 Via del Fosso del Cavaliere, Rome, Italy.

³Istituto di Struttura della Materia-CNR (ISM-CNR), Area della Ricerca di Roma 1, Monterotondo Scalo, Italy.

E-mail: [†]patrick.okeeffe@ism.cnr.it.

type of NC is ultrastable thanks to its protective layer [9,10] and furthermore can exhibit relatively high fluorescence quantum yields. The fluorescence in these NCs is related to the long lived states populated by an energy transfer process between the initially excited metallic core and the organic ligands of the NC. This is in contrast to few atom NCs in which the fluorescence is assigned to transition between states arising from quantum confinement effects [11]. In some rare cases both types of fluorescence has been observed in the same NC [12].

The ability to synthesize atomically precise structures has led to the investigation of the electronic properties of the NCs as a function of their structure and even as a function of substituting individual metal atoms for others. Efforts to precisely control the structure of these systems has culminated in the crystallization of individual gold NCs as first achieved by Jadzinsky *et al.* for the Au₁₀₂(SR)₄₄ leading to the determination of the structure by X-ray crystallography [13]. Since then numerous synthesis protocols have been developed for size focusing of the final NC products and a large number of atomically precise cluster structures have been synthesized [14].

In small NCs the absorption spectrum becomes dominated by discrete optical transitions between molecular orbitals. Indeed a number of works have concentrated on using computational models to perform structure optimization and electronic structure calculations in order to be able to calculate the optical properties of the NCs [1,15–19]. Many of these works have been quite successful in reproducing the static absorption cross-section of individual clusters [1,15–19].

Numerous studies have concentrated on ultrafast studies of gold and silver nanoclusters [20–24,23,25–30] and indeed one of the first studies mentioned ultrafast depolarization of the transient absorption but did not associate it with a measurement of the plasmonicity [21].

An interesting question about the optical excitations of the metallic NCs is how much of the excitation is plasmonic (collective oscillation of the electrons) and how much of the excitation is non-plasmonic (single electron excitation). Furthermore, as the number of atoms in the NC decreases one can observe a transition from a plasmonic to a non-plasmonic type behavior. From an experimental point of view the question has been tackled for both Au [31,32,29,33] and Ag [34–36] NCs with the general consensus being that the transition occurs in the 1.5 - 2.5 nm range for the diameter of the core (e.g. 1.75 - 2.0 nm or 112 to 152 Ag atoms [35], 1.7 - 2.3 nm or 144 to 333 Au atoms [33] and 1.5 - 2.0 nm or 114 to 314 Au atoms [32]). Of course, the transition is not an abrupt change at a single cluster size but rather a gradual change as pointed out by the many theory based studies on the subject [37–40]. Indeed, a recent theory work has concentrated on the introduction of a plasmonicity index in order to provide a measurement of the mixture of plasmonic and non-plasmonic content of optical excitations and used it to characterize optical transitions in both molecules and nanostructures [41,42]. Existing experimental methods used as a probe of plasmonic behavior include inspection of the static UV-Vis absorption [35] and power dependence of the transient absorption [33].

In this work we concentrate on the application of polarization dependent transient absorption spectroscopy to AgNCs to give a further experimental tool to help measure the plasmonicity of optical transitions in these structures. The idea is that plasmonic states lose the memory of the polarization of the exciting radiation due to the ultrafast dephasing of the excited state by electron collisions which is generally expected to occur on a very short timescale (< 100 fs) [43]. Single

Fig. 1 (a) Static UV-Vis absorbance of Ag NPs (b) Static UV-Vis absorbance of Ag NCs. The arrows in (a) and (b) represent the pump photon wavelength for the transient absorption measurement. (c) Transient absorption of Ag NPs with time delays of 0.5, 2 and 10 ps (d) Transient absorption of Ag NCs with time delays of 0.5, 2 and 10 ps.

electron excitations, on the other hand, are mitigated by the dipole transition moment. For example in the case of parallel transitions molecules with their transition dipole moments parallel to the electric field vector of the exciting light are preferentially excited. In isolated single-chromophore organic molecules the fastest depolarization mechanism is rotation of the molecule. In coupled systems depolarization can take place by Forster Resonance Energy Transfer which is generally much faster than rotation. In NCs depolarization may occur by electronic coupling of degenerate excited states or Plasmon induced Resonance Energy Transfer [44].

2 Experimental Methods

The pump-probe experiments were performed using a laser system consisting of a 1 kHz, 4 mJ, 35 fs chirped pulse amplifier seeded by a Ti:Sa oscillator. The pump pulse (405 nm) was produced by frequency doubling of the 810 nm fundamental in a BBO crystal while the probe was generated by focusing a small quantity of 800 nm light ($3 \mu\text{J}$) into a rotating CaF_2 crystal. The optical layout of the commercial transient absorption spectrometer (FemtoFrame II, IB Photonics) consists of a split beam configuration in which 50 % of the white light (350 - 800 nm) passes through the sample contained in a 1 mm static cell while the remainder is used as a reference to account for pulse to pulse fluctuations in the white light generation. The pump pulse is loosely focused (circular spot of diameter= $700 \mu\text{m}$) onto the sample with a power density from 38 to $150 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The spot diameter probe pulse is much smaller (approx. $150 \mu\text{m}$) and its delay time with respect to the

pump pulse is scanned in time by varying the length of its optical path. The instrument response function was measured to be approx. 80 fs.

In order to be sensitive to the depolarization of the photoexcited states discussed above the transient absorption spectra were measured in two polarization states; the first in which the pump and probe pulses are parallel and the second with orthogonal polarizations. If, for example, the linear polarization of the pump pulse creates an aligned ensemble of photoexcited species at early delay times the absorption of the probe polarization parallel to the alignment axis is typically higher than that of probe polarization perpendicular to this axis. As the alignment of the excited state is lost in time the signal depolarizes until there is no difference between the absorption of the parallel and perpendicular polarizations. Thus by comparing these two measurements we can gain information on the depolarization time of the photoexcited state.

Two types of nanostructures were investigated in this work, the synthesis and characterization of which will be described in detail in a future work. Briefly, 4 nm sized Ag dodecanethiolate capped nanoparticles (NPs) were obtained by reducing Ag^+ ions with NaBH_4 in the presence of dodecanethiosulphate molecules whereas 2-3 nm sized Ag dodecanethiolate nanoclusters (NCs) were obtained by reducing the Ag^+ dodecanethiolate complex formed when dodecanethiosulphate is reacted with AgNO_3 . The important difference between the two preparations is that in the first case “naked” Ag^+ ions are reduced to Ag^0 whereas in the second case the reduction occurs on Ag^+ ions bound to dodecanethiosulphate molecules. The static UV-Vis spectra of these samples are shown in Figure 1 (a) and (b).

3 Results and Discussion

The main feature of the static UV-Vis absorbance of the NP sample is plasmonic in nature (see Figure 1 (a)). The peak of the plasmon resonance is at 436 nm which is consistent with AgNPs embedded in DCM (dielectric constant, $\epsilon = 9.08$ at 20 °C) [45] in comparison to the plasmon resonance of AgNPs in water, 395-410 nm ($\epsilon = 80.4$ at 20 °C) and AgNPs in toluene, 460 nm ($\epsilon = 2.4$ at 20 °C) [35]. The static UV-Vis absorbance of the NC sample (see Figure 1 (b)) on the other hand exhibits a much weaker plasmonic band sitting on an intense and broad background absorption. Chakraborty *et al.* [35] interpreted this behavior as an indication of the transition from plasmonic to molecular behavior.

For the transient absorption measurements it was decided to excite the solutions at 405 nm so as to access a component of both the plasmon resonance of the NPs as well as the non-plasmonic components of the NCs with the aim of quantifying the plasmonic/non-plasmonic contributions to the spectrum. The transient absorption spectra at time delays of 0.5, 2 and 10 ps for the perpendicular pump and probe polarizations are shown for the NP and NC species in Figures 1 (c) and (d), respectively. The region of the map between 395 and 420 nm is not visualized in either spectrum as the scattered light from the pump laser dominated this part of the white light probe. In the NP sample one photobleaching region (negative ΔOD) and two photoinduced absorption (positive ΔOD) regions are observed. The negative signal, partially obscured by the pump scattering, is due to plasmon resonance bleaching caused by a change in the dielectric constant of the metal due to electronic heating of the NPs [43]. The two positive wings at higher and lower

Fig. 2 Power dependencies of transient absorption temporal response of (a) NP at 438 nm, (b) NC at 438 nm . The black, red and blue lines correspond to optical pump power densities of 38, 75 and 150 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$, respectively.

wavelengths have the same origin as the change in the dielectric constant broadens the plasmon resonance thus leading to an increase in the absorption in the wings of the resonance. The higher intensity of the blue wing may be due to a contribution from the absorption of excited states. Most of the dynamics are finished by the 10 ps delay. During this time a number of processes take place including electron dephasing (< 10 fs) and thermalization due to electron electron scattering (100s of femtoseconds). These are followed by electron-phonon scattering (< 10 ps) and phonon-phonon scattering (100s ps) which are manifested by recovery of the bleaching signal.

The NC sample also exhibits negative signals in the 370-500 nm range and photoabsorption below 370 nm, however, no photoinduced absorption is observed at > 500 nm. The negative signal in this case could be due to ground state bleaching, excited state emission or indeed in part due to the same plasmon bleaching

Fig. 3 Time cuts from -1 to 12 ps of the intensity of the transient absorption in the parallel and perpendicular polarization states of the (a) NP sample and (b) NC sample averaged over the spectral range from 425 to 455 nm for an optical pump power density of $75 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The signal at delays from 0 - 300 fs is covered by a filled box because of the cross-phase modulation observed in the sample at near zero delay times (see text).

described for the NPs. However, it would seem that the contribution of plasmon bleaching is limited due to the lack of positive signal at wavelengths longer than 500 nm.

As mentioned in the introduction power dependence of the signals have recently been used in the literature as a probe of the onset of metallic behavior in Au NCs. The principle behind this approach is that the dynamics of the plasmon bleaching depends on the intensity of pump because the initial absorption determines the starting electronic temperature of the NP (the higher the initial electronic temperature the slower the dynamics). On the other hand a pure molecular/non-plasmonic signal would consist of single electron transitions. In contrast to the bleaching of the plasmonic resonance the lifetime of the excited state does not depend on the laser pump power but only on the dynamics of the state accessed.

Here we find that both samples display a power dependence to a certain extent (an example of the power dependence is shown in Figure 2 for the probe wavelength of 438 nm) and no clear difference is observed between the two samples. This may be due to the fact that neither sample exhibits pure plasmonic or pure molecular behavior due the similarity of their sizes. Therefore in this case this method is not a sensitive technique to measure the plasmonicity of the optical transitions.

We have therefore applied a new method to the measurement of plasmonic versus non-plasmonic content of the optical transitions in these samples based on the depolarization of the probe absorption. To this end we have measured the transient absorption spectra of both samples in the two different polarization states described in the experimental section, i.e. parallel and orthogonal linear pump probe polarizations. Figure 3 (a) and (b) show the cuts of the transient absorption averaged over the spectral range 425 - 455 nm for the NP and NC samples, respectively. The region < 400 nm was not included in the analysis because of possible distortions due to the contribution of photoinduced absorption of excited states to the signal. Also, we do not consider delays from 0 - 300 fs in order to avoid contamination by the cross-phase modulation observed in the sample at near zero delay times [46]. By visual examination of Figure 3 (a) it is possible to see that apart from the delays at which the cross phase modulation is active the parallel and perpendicular probe intensities are identical. This is due to ultrafast depolarization of the initial interband excitation by electron-electron scattering which are known to occur in NPs on a sub-100 fs timescale [43]. In contrast the parallel and perpendicular polarization signals of the NC sample (see Figure 3 (b)) are significantly different up to delay times of at least 2 ps denoting a molecular type behavior. In fact, in a molecular system such as a metal NC the initial photoexcitation leads to an alignment of the dipole moment of the photoexcited state. This leads to a probe signal that is polarization dependent until the initial anisotropy created by the pump pulse decays.

To quantify the above discussion we extracted the polarization anisotropy at each time delay and at each wavelength in the spectral range of 425 - 455 nm using the standard fluorescence anisotropy formula:

$$r(t) = \frac{I_{\parallel}(t) - I_{\perp}(t)}{I_{\parallel}(t) + 2I_{\perp}(t)} \quad (1)$$

where $r(t)$ is the transient anisotropy, I_{\parallel} is the transient absorption intensity in the geometry with pump and probe polarization parallel and I_{\perp} is the intensity with polarizations perpendicular. The time dependent depolarization signal of the NC sample was then fit by a single exponential and the resulting time τ_{anis} constant was plotted as a function of wavelength in the spectral range of 425 - 455 nm (see dashed line in Figure 4). Clearly this time constant could not be extracted in the case of the NP sample as no anisotropy was observed. The ultrashort timescale (500 ± 120 fs in the range 425 to 455 nm) of the anisotropic decay of the NC sample suggests an ultrafast electronic coupling between excited states. The NC sample anisotropy decay time ranges from 0.4 to 0.8 ps (see Figure 4). Such a timescale is not compatible with rotational depolarization (typically 10s of ps for small molecules) but is consistent with the sub-200 fs depolarization observed by Miller *et al.* [21] in $\text{Au}_{25}\text{L}_{18}^{-}$ monolayer protected clusters which they attributed to internal conversion channels terminating in multiple electronic states with varying transition dipole orientations.

Fig. 4 The lifetime of the anisotropic transient signal of the NC sample is shown as a function of wavelength as a black dashed line (see text for formula). Also shown are the lifetimes of the isotropic transient signal of both the NC (solid blue line) and NP (solid red line) samples as a function of wavelength (see text for formula).

We have also extracted the isotropic transient absorption ($I_{\text{iso}}(t) = I_{\parallel}(t) + 2I_{\perp}(t)$) at each wavelength in the spectral range of 425 - 455 nm and fitted the resulting time dependent signal to a single exponential decay. The resulting time constants τ_{iso} are plotted as a function of wavelength for the NC and NP samples as full lines in Figure 4. The decay times of the isotropic signal varies from 3.1 to 5.2 ps in the case of the NC sample and 0.5-1.8 ps in the case of the NP sample (see Figure 4 (b)). The picosecond lifetimes of these signals are consistent both with plasmonic signals and intramolecular electronic conversion timescales. The shorter lifetime of the NP dynamics may be due to a predominance of the plasmonic dynamics while the slower molecular dynamics dominates in the case of the NC sample. Furthermore, the varying times at different wavelengths can be explained by differing contributions of these processes as a function of the wavelength of the probe.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, we propose a method to distinguish between nanoclusters and nanoparticles, based on the polarization anisotropy of transient absorption. The method has been tested on a dispersion of 4 nm Ag thiolate nanoparticles and a dispersion of 2-3 nm Ag thiolate nanoclusters. While the method is not quantitative it provides complementary information with respect to traditional charac-

terization methods and furthermore will provide very useful information on the transition from plasmonic to molecular behavior of the excited states in nanoclusters. In the nanoclusters examined here we reveal a depolarization time of the transient absorption of 500 fs. Furthermore, we propose that the depolarization time should be very sensitive to the electronic excited state mixing and thus a sensitive measurement of the plasmonic content of resonances in nanoclusters.

Acknowledgements DC and POK acknowledge funding from PRIN project no. 2015CL3APH.

References

1. O. Bakr, V. Amendola, C. Aikens, W. Wenseleers, R. Li, L. DalNegro, G. Schatz, F. Stellacci, *Angewandte Chemie* **121**(32), 6035 (2009). DOI 10.1002/ange.200900298. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ange.200900298>
2. K. Zheng, X. Yuan, N. Goswami, Q. Zhang, J. Xie, *RSC Adv.* **4**, 60581 (2014). DOI 10.1039/C4RA12054J. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C4RA12054J>
3. R. Jin, C. Zeng, M. Zhou, Y. Chen, *Chemical Reviews* **116**(18), 10346 (2016). DOI 10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00703. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.5b00703>.
4. I. Chakraborty, T. Pradeep, *Chemical Reviews* **0**(0), null (0). DOI 10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00769. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00769>
5. S. Choi, R.M. Dickson, J. Yu, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **41**, 1867 (2012). DOI 10.1039/C1CS15226B. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C1CS15226B>
6. Y.S. Chen, H. Choi, P.V. Kamat, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **135**(24), 8822 (2013). DOI 10.1021/ja403807f. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ja403807f>.
7. J. Fang, B. Zhang, Q. Yao, Y. Yang, J. Xie, N. Yan, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* **322**, 1 (2016). DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2016.05.003>. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010854516300066>
8. X. Yuan, Z. Luo, Y. Yu, Q. Yao, J. Xie, *Chemistry - An Asian Journal* **8**(5), 858 (2013). DOI 10.1002/asia.201201236. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/asia.201201236>
9. A. Desireddy, B.E. Conn, J. Guo, B. Yoon, R.N. Barnett, B.M. Monahan, K. Kirschbaum, W.P. Griffith, R.L. Whetten, U. Landman, T.P. Bigioni, *Nature* **501**(7467), 399 (2013). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature12523>.
10. B.E. Conn, A. Desireddy, A. Atmagulov, S. Wickramasinghe, B. Bhattarai, B. Yoon, R.N. Barnett, Y. Abdollahian, Y.W. Kim, W.P. Griffith, S.R.J. Oliver, U. Landman, T.P. Bigioni, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **119**(20), 11238 (2015). DOI 10.1021/jp512237b. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp512237b>
11. J. Zheng, C. Zhou, M. Yu, J. Liu, *Nanoscale* **4**, 4073 (2012). DOI 10.1039/C2NR31192E. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C2NR31192E>
12. M.S. Devadas, J. Kim, E. Sinn, D. Lee, T. Goodson, G. Ramakrishna, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **114**(51), 22417 (2010). DOI 10.1021/jp107033n. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp107033n>
13. P.D. Jadzinsky, G. Calero, C.J. Ackerson, D.A. Bushnell, R.D. Kornberg, **318**(5849), 430 (2007). DOI 10.1126/science.1148624
14. T. Udayabhaskararao, T. Pradeep, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* **4**(9), 1553 (2013). DOI 10.1021/jz400332g. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jz400332g>.
15. C.M. Aikens, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **112**(50), 19797 (2008). DOI 10.1021/jp8090914. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp8090914>
16. H. Yang, Y. Wang, H. Huang, L. Gell, L. Lehtovaara, S. Malola, H. Häkkinen, N. Zheng, *Nature Communications* **4**, 2422 EP (2013). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms3422>.
17. P.N. Day, R. Pachter, K.A. Nguyen, T.P. Bigioni, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A* **120**(4), 507 (2016). DOI 10.1021/acs.jpca.5b09623. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.5b09623>. PMID: 26730764
18. H. Yang, Y. Wang, X. Chen, X. Zhao, L. Gu, H. Huang, J. Yan, C. Xu, G. Li, J. Wu, A.J. Edwards, B. Dittrich, Z. Tang, D. Wang, L. Lehtovaara, H. Häkkinen, N. Zheng, *Nature Communications* **7**, 12809 EP (2016). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12809>.
19. S.H. Yau, B.A. Ashenfelter, A. Desireddy, A.P. Ashwell, O. Varnavski, G.C. Schatz, T.P. Bigioni, T. Goodson, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **121**(2), 1349 (2017). DOI 10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b10434. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b10434>

20. S. Link, M.A. El-Sayed, T.G. Schaaff, R.L. Whetten, *Chemical Physics Letters* **356**(34), 240 (2002). DOI [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614\(02\)00306-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2614(02)00306-8). URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0009261402003068>
21. S.A. Miller, J.M. Womick, J.F. Parker, R.W. Murray, A.M. Moran, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **113**(22), 9440 (2009). DOI 10.1021/jp9025046. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp9025046>
22. H. Qian, M.Y. Sfeir, R. Jin, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **114**(47), 19935 (2010). DOI 10.1021/jp107915x. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp107915x>
23. C. Yi, M.A. Tofanelli, C.J. Ackerson, K.L. Knappenberger, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **135**(48), 18222 (2013). DOI 10.1021/ja409998j. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ja409998j>
24. T.D. Green, K.L. Knappenberger, *Nanoscale* **4**, 4111 (2012). DOI 10.1039/C2NR31080E. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C2NR31080E>
25. S.H. Yau, O. Varnavski, T. Goodson, *Accounts of Chemical Research* **46**(7), 1506 (2013). DOI 10.1021/ar300280w. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ar300280w>
26. S. Mustalahti, P. Myllyperkiö, T. Lahtinen, K. Salorinne, S. Malola, J. Koivisto, H. Häkkinen, M. Pettersson, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **118**(31), 18233 (2014). DOI 10.1021/jp505464z. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp505464z>
27. K.G. Stamplecoskie, P.V. Kamat, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **136**(31), 11093 (2014). DOI 10.1021/ja505361n. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ja505361n>
28. M. Zhou, J. Zhong, S. Wang, Q. Guo, M. Zhu, Y. Pei, A. Xia, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **119**(32), 18790 (2015). DOI 10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b05376. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b05376>
29. C. Yi, H. Zheng, L.M. Tvedte, C.J. Ackerson, K.L. Knappenberger, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **119**(11), 6307 (2015). DOI 10.1021/jp512112z. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp512112z>
30. T. Stoll, E. Sgrò, J.W. Jarrett, J. Réhault, A. Oriana, L. Sala, F. Branchi, G. Cerullo, K.L. Knappenberger, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **138**(6), 1788 (2016). DOI 10.1021/jacs.5b12621. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5b12621>
31. R. Philip, P. Chantharasupawong, H. Qian, R. Jin, J. Thomas, *Nano Letters* **12**(9), 4661 (2012). DOI 10.1021/nl301988v. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/nl301988v>
32. S. Malola, L. Lehtovaara, J. Enkovaara, H. Häkkinen, *ACS Nano* **7**(11), 10263 (2013). DOI 10.1021/nm4046634. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/nm4046634>
33. M. Zhou, C. Zeng, Y. Chen, S. Zhao, M.Y. Sfeir, M. Zhu, R. Jin, *Nature Communications* **7**, 13240 EP (2016). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13240>
34. J.A. Scholl, A.L. Koh, J.A. Dionne, *Nature* **483**(7390), 421 (2012). DOI 10.1038/nature10904. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature10904>
35. I. Chakraborty, J. Erusappan, A. Govindarajan, K.S. Sugi, T. Udayabhaskararao, A. Ghosh, T. Pradeep, *Nanoscale* **6**, 8024 (2014). DOI 10.1039/C4NR00679H. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C4NR00679H>
36. T. Lunsken, P. Heister, M. Thamer, C.A. Walenta, A. Kartouzian, U. Heiz, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **17**, 17541 (2015). DOI 10.1039/C5CP01582K. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C5CP01582K>
37. G. Piccini, R.W.A. Havenith, R. Broer, M. Stener, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **117**(33), 17196 (2013). DOI 10.1021/jp405769e. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp405769e>
38. E.B. Guidez, C.M. Aikens, *Nanoscale* **6**, 11512 (2014). DOI 10.1039/C4NR02225D. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C4NR02225D>
39. J. Ma, Z. Wang, L.W. Wang, *Nature Communications* **6**, 10107 EP (2015). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10107>
40. Titantah, John T., Karttunen, Mikko, *Eur. Phys. J. B* **89**(5), 125 (2016). DOI 10.1140/epjb/e2016-70065-y. URL <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjb/e2016-70065-y>
41. L. Bursi, A. Calzolari, S. Corni, E. Molinari, *ACS Photonics* **3**(4), 520 (2016). DOI 10.1021/acsphotonics.5b00688. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acsphotonics.5b00688>
42. R. Zhang, L. Bursi, J.D. Cox, Y. Cui, C.M. Krauter, A. Alabastri, A. Manjavacas, A. Calzolari, S. Corni, E. Molinari, E.A. Carter, F.J. García de Abajo, H. Zhang, P. Nordlander, *ACS Nano* **0**(0), null (0). DOI 10.1021/acsnano.7b03421. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.7b03421>
43. G.V. Hartland, *Chemical Reviews* **111**(6), 3858 (2011). DOI 10.1021/cr1002547. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/cr1002547>

-
44. J. Li, S.K. Cushing, F. Meng, T.R. Senty, A.D. Bristow, N. Wu, *Nat Photon* **9**(9), 601 (2015). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nphoton.2015.142>.
 45. R.C. Weast (ed.), *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics* (CRC Press, 1982)
 46. M. Lorenc, M. Ziolk, R. Naskrecki, J. Karolczak, J. Kubicki, A. Maciejewski, *Applied Physics B* **74**(1), 19 (2002). URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003400100750>